

Alternate partial root-zone N-fertigation increases water use efficiency and N uptake of barley at elevated CO₂

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Xiying Zhang

Keywords:

Elevated CO₂
N-fertigation
Water use efficiency
Growth
N nutrition

ABSTRACT

Elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentration (e[CO₂]) increases water use efficiency (WUE) while reducing nitrogen (N) concentration of crops particularly under drought conditions; yet the combined effects of e[CO₂] and different N-fertigation regimes on WUE and crop N nutrition remain largely elusive. In this experiment, the growth and physiological responses of two barley genotypes, wild type barley Steptoe (WT) and its correspondent ABA-deficient mutant barley Az34, to three N-fertigation regimes at ambient CO₂ (a[CO₂]) (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm) were investigated. From tillering to grain filling stage, the plants were subjected to three N-fertigation regimes: 1) N-fertigation at full irrigation volume (FIN); 2) N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume (DIN); 3) alternate N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume (PRDN). Although e[CO₂] had little effect on g_s, T_r and plant water use of WT, especially under DIN and PRDN, it increased A_n, resulting in an increased WUE at stomatal, leaf and whole plant levels. For Az34, the positive effect of e[CO₂] on WUE was attributed to both significantly enhanced A_n and lowered g_s and T_r. For both genotypes, e[CO₂] increased 100-grain weight and shoot dry biomass but didn't affect grain yield and WUE for grain production (WUE_g). PRDN increased grain yield, HI and WUE_g of both genotypes regardless of [CO₂], compared to FIN. DIN and PRDN increased N uptake of both genotypes at e[CO₂] compared to FIN. Compared to a[CO₂], e[CO₂] increased ¹⁵N uptake and ¹⁵N recovery rate of both genotypes by enhancing plant biomass. In addition, both genotypes grown under DIN and PRDN allocated more N to the grain compared to the FIN plants. Collectively, N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume promoted N allocation to the grain and increased WUE, particularly under e[CO₂]. Such information is conducive for optimizing WUE and N nutrition of crops in a future water-limited and CO₂-enriched environment.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the effect of rising atmospheric CO₂ concentration ([CO₂]) on crop yield and quality has received increased attention. According to IPCC (2014), the [CO₂] will rise to 720 ppm by the end of this century. The elevated [CO₂] (e[CO₂]) in atmosphere may contribute to changes in global climate, such as global warming and precipitation patterns, which can reduce the availability of soil water in many regions of the world (Wigley and Raper, 1992; Keeling et al., 1995; Widodo et al., 2003). Water use efficiency (WUE) is defined as the ratio of photosynthetic carbon assimilation to transpiration rate or biomass

accumulation to plant water consumption (Bacon, 2004), which is affected by stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration rate (T_r) and /or photosynthetic rate (A_n) (Farquhar et al., 1989). In most plant species, notably C₃ species, e[CO₂] increases A_n and growth while decreasing stomatal conductance (g_s) hence transpiration rate (T_r) hereby increases WUE (Ainsworth and Rogers, 2007; Leakey et al., 2009; Taub, 2010; Mamatha et al., 2014). The enhanced A_n of plants grown under e[CO₂] is due partially to the depressed photorespiration by increasing the ratio of CO₂ to O₂ at the chloroplast, which stimulates carboxylation reaction and inhibits oxygenation reaction of Rubisco (Long et al., 2004; Ainsworth and Rogers, 2007). On the other hand, the e[CO₂] can decrease g_s,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2021.107168>

Received 24 February 2021; Received in revised form 27 July 2021; Accepted 4 September 2021

Available online 15 September 2021

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but the reduction in g_s is greater under well-watered conditions than under drought stress (Wall et al., 2001; Gunderson et al., 2002; Mamatha et al., 2014). Similarly, a greater reduction in g_s of maize plants was observed under drought at $a[CO_2]$ compared to that at $e[CO_2]$ (Leakey et al., 2006).

Deficit irrigation (DI), irrigating the crop with an amount of water less than potential evapotranspiration, is considered as a water-saving irrigation technique which can reduce crop water use with minor or no yield loss (English and Raja, 1996). Partial root-zone drying (PRD) irrigation is a method that irrigates half of the root system while the other half allows drying to a predetermined level before alternate irrigation (Liu et al., 2006). Although both DI and PRD are considered as water-saving irrigation strategies, many studies have shown that PRD is superior to DI in terms of maintaining yield and improving WUE when the same amount of water is applied (Kirda et al., 2004, 2007a, 2007b; Dodd, 2007; Topcu et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2010; Kaman et al., 2011; Kaman and Özbek, 2016; Kaman and Kirda, 2017). Wang et al. (2010) found that PRD led to higher photosynthetic rate (A_n), xylem sap ABA concentration and WUE than DI given a same irrigation volume. Sadras (2009) conducted a meta-analysis to compare the irrigation water productivity (IWP) of PRD and DI, and the results showed that both DI and PRD increased IWP, on average, by 76% and 82%, respectively, as compared to full irrigation controls.

Previous studies have shown that the $e[CO_2]$ can decrease nitrogen (N) concentration of crops particularly under drought conditions (Taub and Wang, 2008). One reason for the lowered crop N concentration when grown at $e[CO_2]$ is the dilution of N by increased plant biomass accumulation (Gifford et al., 2000). It is well known that the uptake of N through transpiration driven mass flow depends on the transpiration rate and N ion concentration in the rhizosphere (Barber, 1995; Pihak, 2003). The $e[CO_2]$ could cause decrease in N uptake rate per unit mass or length of root due to decreased transpiration hence the mass flow of nitrate (McDonald et al., 2002). Nonetheless, our previous studies have demonstrated that PRD irrigation induced drying/rewetting cycles of the soil profile could improve soil N availability and N uptake in tomato and potato plants, especially N concentration of upper leaves, leading to a higher A_n hence WUE as compared with DI (Wang et al., 2010, 2013a). Also, Kirda et al. (2005) reported that PRD had higher N-fertiliser recovery of maize compared with DI and FI. Thus, it is plausible to suggest that PRD irrigation might be able to ameliorate the negative effect of $e[CO_2]$ on crop N nutrition. Moreover, the direct and simultaneous delivery of water and nutrients to plants through fertigation could improve both WUE and nutrient use efficiency. For instance, Wang et al. (2018) reported that optimized water and N in fertigation improved WUE and plant N nutrition. Therefore, by application of PRD in combination with N-fertigation, both water use efficiency (WUE) and crop N uptake could be improved, which may be used as novel water and N management strategies for sustainable agricultural development in future climate change scenarios.

It is well known that PRD and DI can induce root ABA signal to regulate plant growth and water consumption thereby increasing WUE (Wang et al., 2010). However, the role of endogenous ABA signaling in $e[CO_2]$ -induced g_s reduction is controversial. Chater et al. (2015) revealed that $e[CO_2]$ caused stomatal movement of *Arabidopsis thaliana* involves ABA signaling; while Hsu et al. (2018) found that $e[CO_2]$ could induce stomatal closure of *Arabidopsis thaliana* via an ABA-independent pathway downstream of OST1 kinase. Yan et al. (2017) reported that the g_s of tomato grown at moderate drought stress was mostly mediated by root-to-shoot ABA signaling under $a[CO_2]$ while it became insensitive to ABA and was regulated predominately by turgor pressure under $e[CO_2]$. In short term, $e[CO_2]$ decreases g_s mainly by inducing stomatal closure (Ainsworth and Rogers, 2007; Chater et al., 2015); in long term, the decreased g_s at $e[CO_2]$ is attributed to both the reduced stomatal density and stomatal aperture (Ainsworth and Rogers, 2007). Moreover, our recent studies have revealed that the endogenous ABA level of plants played an essential role in modulating the response of g_s to soil water

deficits under $e[CO_2]$, though the effect was species dependent (Fang et al., 2019; Wei et al., 2020). $e[CO_2]$ sensitized g_s reduction in wild type barley but retarded it in wild type tomato plants, whereas such effects were absent in their correspondent ABA-deficient mutants, viz., *Az34* and *flacca*.

Earlier studies have shown that the WUE of tomato plants could be enhanced by reduced irrigation combined with $e[CO_2]$ (Pazzagli et al., 2016). However, the combined effects of $e[CO_2]$ and different N-fertigation regimes on WUE and crop N nutrition remain largely elusive, particularly the role of endogenous ABA level in mediating those responses has not been researched. In the present study, two barley genotypes with contrasting endogenous ABA levels, viz., wild type (WT) and its correspondent ABA-deficient mutant (*Az34*), were used. The objective was to explore the effect of three different N-fertigation regimes in combination with two CO_2 concentrations (400 ppm and 800 ppm) on WUE and N uptake of barley plants differing in endogenous ABA levels. It was hypothesized that N-fertigation in PRD mode would further enhance WUE while sustaining plant N nutrition under $e[CO_2]$, where endogenous ABA level would play a role in modulating the effects of the fertigation regimes on plant WUE and N nutrition under $e[CO_2]$.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental setup

The experiment was conducted from January to June 2020 in two greenhouse cells with different CO_2 concentrations, that was, the control cell with ambient $[CO_2]$ (400 ppm, $a[CO_2]$) and a cell with elevated $[CO_2]$ (800 ppm, $e[CO_2]$) at University of Copenhagen, Taastrup, Denmark (12.18°E, 55.40°N). In both greenhouse cells, the $[CO_2]$ was monitored every six seconds by a CO_2 Transmitter Series GMT220 (Vaisala Group, Helsinki, Finland). The actual CO_2 concentrations during the experimental period are shown in Fig. 1. The climatic conditions in the greenhouse were set as: the air temperature of $25/16 \pm 2^\circ C$ day/night, 60% relative humidity, 16 h photoperiod, and $> 500 \mu mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$ photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) supplied by sunlight plus LED lamps. Two barley genotypes were used as plant materials, including wild type barley Steptoe (WT) and ABA-deficient mutant barley *Az34*. The mixed air-dried clay soil and sandy loam soil (1:1 by mass) was used in the present experiment with a pH of 6.35, total N $1.2 g kg^{-1}$, available P $22 mg kg^{-1}$ and available K $63.75 mg kg^{-1}$. The soil water holding capacity (SWHC) and permanent wilting point calculated on the volumetric basis were 30% and 5% (vol.). The size of the pots was 4 L (15 cm in diameter and 25 cm in depth). A plastic sheet was used to divide the pots vertically into two equal compartments, allowing no water

Fig. 1. Actual atmospheric CO_2 concentrations ($[CO_2]$) of cell 1 (400 ppm) and cell 2 (800 ppm) during the experimental period.

exchange between them, thus creating two separated irrigation compartments. 60 barley seeds of each genotype were sown on 28th January 2020 (30 seeds of each genotype in a[CO₂] and 30 seeds of each genotype in e[CO₂]) in nursery trays, and at four leaf stage, fifteen uniform and robust barley seedlings for each genotype in each greenhouse cell (total sixty plants) were transplanted to the pots (one plant per pot) on 17th February 2020.

2.2. N-fertilization treatments

The barley plants were well-watered to 90% SWHC in the first six weeks after transplanting. From tillering to grain filling stage, the plants were subjected to three N-fertilization regimes: 1) N-fertilization at full irrigation volume (FIN), in which the soil water holding capacity was maintained at 90%; 2) N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume (DIN), where 70% of water consumption of FIN was irrigated to the whole pot; 3) alternate N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume (PRDN), where 70% of water consumption of FIN was irrigated to only half of the pot until the soil water content of the dry side decreased to 7%–10%, then the irrigation was shifted to the dry side. The experiment included 12 treatments in total and 5 replicates of each treatment. Every plant (pot) was applied with 1 g N fertilizer (NH₄NO₃) during the whole growth period. To trace the uptake of N, ¹⁵NH₄¹⁵NO₃ was used at the enrichment of 5%. In addition, each pot received 3.49 g KH₂PO₄ (1 g K pot⁻¹ and 0.79 g P pot⁻¹) to meet the macronutrient requirement for plant growth. All the P and K fertilizers as well as 20% N fertilizer were applied as basal fertilizers, and they were dissolved in tap water and irrigated evenly on both soil compartments after filling the pots. The remaining N fertilizer (80% of N fertilizer, 0.8 g N) was applied during N-fertilization treatment. The N-fertilization treatments were conducted from 31st March to 17th May, and all of the plants were at the late grain filling stage by the end of the treatments. Although the plants consumed

very little amount of water per day, in order to avoid severe soil water deficits that may damage the root system, 50 ml water was supplied to each pot evenly every two days to maintain the soil water content at ca. 12% on average until plant harvest on the 1st June. During the N-fertilization period, N fertilizer was delivered with irrigation water on 7, 10, 13, 15, 22, 27 days after N-fertilization treatment (DAT), 6 times in total.

During the experimental period, soil water content (θ) of both compartments was recorded daily (between 13:00–15:00) before irrigation using a time domain reflectometry (TDR, TRASE, Soil Moisture Equipment Corp., CA, USA). Each compartment was installed with a soil moisture probe (20 cm in length) to determine soil water content. The water consumption of FIN treatment was used to calculate irrigation amount of DIN and PRDN treatments with consideration of genotype and [CO₂]. Changes of averaged daily soil water content (vol.%) in the pots under different experimental treatments are shown in Fig. 2.

2.3. Sampling, measurements and analysis

Net photosynthetic rate (A_n), stomatal conductance (g_s) and transpiration rate (T_r) were measured on upper fully expanded leaves using a portable photosynthesis system (LI-6400, Li-Cor Biosciences, NB, USA) from 9:00–11:00 am once a week during the N-fertilization treatment. Intrinsic water use efficiency (WUE_{int}) and instantaneous water use efficiency (WUE_{ins}) were estimated as A_n/g_s and A_n/T_r , respectively. Leaf water potential was measured by a Scholander-type pressure chamber (Model 3000F01H12G2P40, Soil Moisture Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, CA, USA) on the 18th and 38th DAT. Fresh samples of leaves were collected on the 18th and 38th DAT and immediately kept at -80 °C for ABA analysis. Leaf ABA concentrations ($[ABA]_{leaf}$) were measured by ELISA method according to Asch (2000). Plants were harvested at maturity stage. Stems, leaves, kernels and roots were collected separately and then determined after oven drying at 70 °C

Fig. 2. Changes of averaged daily soil water content (vol. %) of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34; Az34 was expressed as “A” in the present figure) under three N-fertilization regimes (N-fertilization at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) (a, b) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm) (c, d). PRDN-L and PRDN-R denote the left and the right soil compartment of the PRDN pots, respectively.

(stems, leaves and roots) or air drying (kernels) to constant weight. Water use efficiency at biomass level (WUE_b) and at grain yield level (WUE_g) were calculated as the ratio of aboveground dry biomass and grain yield to plant water use during the experimental period.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed by three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS 25.0 (IBM Corporation, New York, USA) for the independent variables: Genotype, $[CO_2]$ and N-fertilization regimes. One-way ANOVA and Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% confidence level was further used when their significant interactions between the independent variables to test for significant differences between treatments. Before any analysis, we checked to make sure that the data was normally distributed by using the Shapiro-Wilks test, and to test homogeneity of variance we used Levene's test.

3. Results

3.1. Leaf gas exchange, WUE_{int} and WUE_{ins}

A_n was significantly affected by $[CO_2]$, N-fertilization and the interaction between genotype and $[CO_2]$. However, g_s and T_r were significantly affected by all factors as well as the interaction between genotype and $[CO_2]$ (Fig. 3; Table 1). The A_n of WT and Az34 increased by 68.3% and 30.1%, respectively, at e $[CO_2]$ compared to that at a $[CO_2]$. For N-fertilization treatments, DIN and PRDN decreased A_n of WT by 31% and 24.6% at a $[CO_2]$ and by 19.7% and 10.7% at e $[CO_2]$, respectively, compared to FIN. However, A_n of Az34 grown under DIN and PRDN was decreased by 21.9% and 18.2%, respectively, at a $[CO_2]$ but only by 2.3% and 2.9%, respectively, at e $[CO_2]$, compared to that under FIN (Fig. 3a). In addition, e $[CO_2]$ significantly decreased g_s and T_r of Az34 by 41.7% and 34.2%, respectively, while it had no significant effect on that of WT, compared to a $[CO_2]$. g_s and T_r of Az34 were on average 64.2% and 49.9% higher than that of WT, respectively, at a $[CO_2]$; but there was no significant difference in g_s and T_r between the two genotypes at e

$[CO_2]$. However, DIN and PRDN significantly decreased g_s and T_r of both genotypes at a $[CO_2]$ compared to FIN. At e $[CO_2]$, a slight but not significant decrease in g_s and T_r of both genotypes was observed under DIN and PRDN compared to FIN (Fig. 3b, c).

WUE_{int} was significantly affected by all factors and WUE_{ins} was significantly affected by genotype and $[CO_2]$ (Fig. 3d, e; Table 1). e $[CO_2]$ significantly increased WUE_{int} and WUE_{ins} by 97% and 85.5%, respectively, compared to a $[CO_2]$. Moreover, WT had higher WUE_{int} and WUE_{ins} than Az34. WUE_{int} of FIN treatment was significantly lower than that of DIN and PRDN treatments.

3.2. Leaf water potential and leaf ABA concentration

Leaf water potential (LWP) was significantly affected by $[CO_2]$ and N-fertilization treatments (Table 1). Plants grown under FIN treatment had a higher LWP than that under DIN and PRDN treatments. When the plants suffered from drought stress (e.g., under DIN or PRDN treatments), e $[CO_2]$ increased LWP of both genotypes compared to a $[CO_2]$ (Fig. 4a). Leaf ABA concentration ($[ABA]_{leaf}$) was significantly affected by N-fertilization treatments and genotypes (Table 1). Plants of both genotypes grown under N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume had higher $[ABA]_{leaf}$ than FIN plants (Fig. 4b). As expected, WT had higher $[ABA]_{leaf}$ than Az34 at a $[CO_2]$ (Fig. 4b).

3.3. Shoot dry biomass, root dry biomass, root-shoot ratio, plant water use and WUE_b

Shoot dry biomass was significantly affected by $[CO_2]$ and N-fertilization treatments (Table 2). The e $[CO_2]$ improved shoot dry biomass by 20.1% compared to a $[CO_2]$ across the genotype and N-fertilization regimes. Compared to FIN plants, a less reduction in shoot dry biomass caused by N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume of WT was observed at e $[CO_2]$ (6% in DIN and 2% in PRDN) compared to that at a $[CO_2]$ (23% in DIN and 8% in PRDN) (Table 2). Root dry biomass was only affected by genotype, with Az34 having higher root dry biomass than WT (Table 2). Root-shoot ratio was affected by genotype, $[CO_2]$ as

Fig. 3. The averaged net photosynthetic rate (A_n), stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration rate (T_r), WUE_{int} (A_n/g_s) and WUE_{ins} (A_n/T_r) of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertilization regimes (N-fertilization at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a $[CO_2]$ (400 ppm) and e $[CO_2]$ (800 ppm). Different letters on the columns indicate statistically significant differences among the treatments by Duncan's test at $p < 0.05$.

Table 1

Significant probabilities for variables and the interaction of factors analyzed according to three-way ANOVA by Duncan's test. *, **, *** and ns denote significances at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$ and no significance, respectively.

	Genotype	[CO ₂]	N-fertiligation	Genotype × [CO ₂]	Genotype × N-fertiligation	[CO ₂] × N-fertiligation	Genotype × [CO ₂] × N-fertiligation
A _n	ns	***	***	**	ns	ns	ns
g _s	***	***	***	***	ns	ns	ns
T _r	***	***	***	***	ns	ns	ns
WUE _{int}	*	***	*	ns	ns	ns	ns
WUE _{ins}	*	***	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
LWP	ns	***	***	ns	ns	**	ns
ABA	***	ns	***	ns	ns	ns	ns
N uptake	*	***	ns	*	*	*	ns
¹⁵ N uptake	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
¹⁵ N recovery rate	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
N partitioning-L	*	ns	*	ns	*	ns	ns
N partitioning-S	ns	*	***	ns	*	ns	ns
N partitioning-G	ns	*	**	ns	*	ns	ns

Note: A_n: photosynthetic rate; g_s: stomatal conductance; T_r: transpiration rate; WUE_{int}: intrinsic water use efficiency; WUE_{ins}: instantaneous water use efficiency; LWP: leaf water potential; ABA: abscisic acid; N partitioning-L: N partitioning to leaf; N partitioning-S: N partitioning to stem; N partitioning-G: N partitioning to grain.

Fig. 4. The averaged leaf water potential (LWP) and leaf ABA concentrations ($[ABA]_{leaf}$) of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertiligation regimes (N-fertiligation at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertiligation at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertiligation at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm). Different letters on the columns indicate statistically significant differences among the treatments by Duncan's test at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2

Shoot dry biomass, root dry biomass, root-shoot ratio (R/S), plant water use and WUE_p of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertiligation regimes (N-fertiligation at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertiligation at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertiligation at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm). Values are means ± SE (n = 5). Significant probabilities for variables and the interaction of factors were analyzed according to three-way ANOVA by Duncan's test. Different letters in the same column indicate statistically significant differences among the treatments by Duncan's test at $p < 0.05$. *, ** and ns denote significances at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ and no significance, respectively.

Genotype	[CO ₂]	N-fertiligation	Shoot dry biomass (g pot ⁻¹)	Root dry biomass (g pot ⁻¹)	R/S	Plant water use (L pot ⁻¹)	WUE _p (g L ⁻¹)
WT	400	FIN	44.48 ± 2.20	1.72 ± 0.14c	0.04 ± 0.004cd	11.19 ± 0.48bc	3.97 ± 0.06
		DIN	34.18 ± 0.82	1.30 ± 0.43c	0.04 ± 0.012cd	8.67 ± 0.28e	3.96 ± 0.14
		PRDN	41.03 ± 0.82	2.72 ± 0.88abc	0.07 ± 0.021abcd	9.08 ± 0.18e	4.53 ± 0.17
	800	FIN	52.38 ± 3.80	2.31 ± 0.60c	0.04 ± 0.010cd	11.27 ± 0.99bc	4.69 ± 0.26
		DIN	49.22 ± 1.79	3.49 ± 0.97abc	0.07 ± 0.020abcd	9.02 ± 0.30e	5.47 ± 0.22
		PRDN	51.17 ± 1.35	1.23 ± 0.11c	0.02 ± 0.002d	8.93 ± 0.22e	5.74 ± 0.19
Az34	400	FIN	47.63 ± 4.15	5.00 ± 1.48ab	0.10 ± 0.027ab	13.73 ± 0.66a	3.47 ± 0.25
		DIN	43.82 ± 4.46	5.26 ± 1.09a	0.11 ± 0.020a	10.60 ± 0.45cd	4.09 ± 0.28
		PRDN	44.87 ± 1.63	3.72 ± 0.29abc	0.08 ± 0.006abc	10.75 ± 0.23cd	4.18 ± 0.15
	800	FIN	55.84 ± 3.14	3.19 ± 0.59abc	0.06 ± 0.011bcd	12.53 ± 0.37ab	4.45 ± 0.18
		DIN	49.27 ± 3.40	3.66 ± 0.89abc	0.07 ± 0.016abcd	9.23 ± 0.53e	5.34 ± 0.21
		PRDN	49.50 ± 1.29	2.65 ± 0.73bc	0.05 ± 0.014bcd	9.71 ± 0.04de	5.10 ± 0.12
ANOVA analysis							
Genotype			ns	***	***	***	*
[CO ₂]			***	ns	*	*	***
N-fertiligation			*	ns	ns	***	***
Genotype × [CO ₂]			ns	*	*	*	ns
Genotype × N-fertiligation			ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
[CO ₂] × N-fertiligation			ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Genotype × [CO ₂] × N-fertiligation			ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

well as the interaction between genotype and $[\text{CO}_2]$. At $a[\text{CO}_2]$, Az34 had the highest root-shoot ratio under DIN conditions among all treatments. Plant water use was significantly affected by all factors as well as the interaction between genotype and $[\text{CO}_2]$ (Table 2). The $e[\text{CO}_2]$ decreased plant water use of Az34 by 10.3% while it had little effect on plant water use of WT compared to $a[\text{CO}_2]$. Plants of both genotypes grown under DIN and PRDN had a lower plant water use than that under FIN treatment. Across the N-fertilization treatments, plant water use of Az34 was on average 21.2% higher than that of WT at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ but there was no significant difference in plant water use between the two genotypes at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ (Table 2). WUE_b was significantly affected by all factors (Table 2). The $e[\text{CO}_2]$ increased WUE_b by 27.3% compared to $a[\text{CO}_2]$. WT had higher WUE_b than Az34 (6.2% at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ and 6.7% at $e[\text{CO}_2]$). WUE_b of plants treated with DIN and PRDN treatments was 13.8% and 17.9%, respectively, higher than that of FIN treatment (Table 2). In addition, across all treatments, WUE_b was significantly positively related to WUE_{ins} and WUE_{int} (Fig. 5).

3.4. Hundred-grain weight, grain yield, harvest index and WUE_g

Hundred-grain weight was only significantly affected by $[\text{CO}_2]$, being on average 8% higher at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ than that at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ (Table 3). Grain yield was significantly affected by N-fertilization regimes, with DIN and PRDN treatments increasing grain yield by 20.3% and 31.5%, respectively, compared to FIN treatment, across the $[\text{CO}_2]$ and genotypes (Table 3). Harvest index (HI) was significantly affected by all factors. The $e[\text{CO}_2]$ decreased HI by 22.4% compared to $a[\text{CO}_2]$. HI of plants grown under DIN and PRDN was 29.4% and 39.7% higher than that under FIN, respectively. Across $[\text{CO}_2]$ and N-fertilization treatments, WT showed higher HI than Az34 (Table 3). WUE_g was significantly affected by genotype and N-fertilization. DIN and PRDN treatments improved WUE_g by 46% and 64%, respectively, compared to FIN treatment, across the $[\text{CO}_2]$ and genotypes. WT had higher WUE_g than Az34, across $[\text{CO}_2]$ and N-fertilization treatments (Table 3).

3.5. $\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ uptake, ^{15}N partitioning and ^{15}N recovery rate

Compared to $a[\text{CO}_2]$, the $e[\text{CO}_2]$ increased N uptake of WT under DIN and PRDN treatments (Fig. 6a). For WT, DIN and PRDN plants had lower N uptake than FIN plants at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ but had a slight increase in N uptake compared to FIN plants at $e[\text{CO}_2]$. The N uptake of Az34 was not significantly affected by N-fertilization regimes or $[\text{CO}_2]$. At $a[\text{CO}_2]$, WT had higher N uptake than Az34 under FIN treatment while there was no significant difference between two genotypes under DIN and PRDN

treatments. At $e[\text{CO}_2]$, an increase in N uptake of WT was observed compared to that of Az34 (Fig. 6a). ^{15}N uptake was only affected by $[\text{CO}_2]$. Across the genotypes and N-fertilization regimes, the $e[\text{CO}_2]$ increased ^{15}N uptake of plants as compared with $a[\text{CO}_2]$ (Fig. 6b).

^{15}N partitioning among plant organs in barley affected by genotypes, N-fertilization regimes and $[\text{CO}_2]$ is shown in Fig. 7. The percentage of ^{15}N partitioned to the leaf of Az34 was decreased by DIN and PRDN while that of WT was not affected by N-fertilization treatments. The percentage of ^{15}N partitioned to the leaf of Az34 was higher than that of WT under FIN treatment while that was similar in both genotypes under DIN and PRDN. The percentage of ^{15}N partitioned to the leaf was not affected by $[\text{CO}_2]$. The percentage of ^{15}N partitioned to the stem of Az34 was significantly decreased by DIN and PRDN while that of WT was not affected by N-fertilization regimes. Under DIN and PRDN, Az34 allocated more N to grain and a slight increase in the percentage of ^{15}N partitioned to the grain of WT, compared to FIN plants. In addition, a slight decrease in the percentage of ^{15}N partitioned to the grain of both genotypes at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ compared to that at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ was noticed. ^{15}N recovery rate was only significantly affected by $[\text{CO}_2]$, where $e[\text{CO}_2]$ increased ^{15}N recovery rate compared to $a[\text{CO}_2]$ (Fig. 8).

4. Discussion

It is well known that soil water deficit can decrease g_s of plants (Liu et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2010; Pazzagli et al., 2016). Consistent with this, the results of the present study showed that DIN and PRDN decreased g_s of both genotypes compared to FIN treatment, especially at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ (Fig. 3b). As expected, A_n of WT grown under DIN and PRDN was significantly decreased compared to that under FIN treatment regardless of $[\text{CO}_2]$, which was attributed mainly to stomatal limitation on the photosynthesis caused by the decrease in g_s under soil water deficit (Fig. 3b), in line with the findings of previous studies (Liu et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2013b). The increased WUE at stomatal level (WUE_{int}) was usually observed under reduced irrigation (Liu et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2010; Pazzagli et al., 2016), owing to a relatively less reduction in A_n than in g_s caused by soil water deficits. Likewise, here a significant increase in WUE_{int} of both genotypes under DIN and PRDN in relation to FIN, especially at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ was observed (Fig. 3d). Most interestingly, across the $[\text{CO}_2]$ treatments and genotypes, PRDN increased WUE_{int} by an average of 6.3% than DIN in accordance with the finding of previous studies (Wang et al., 2010; Pazzagli et al., 2016).

Early studies have shown that the $e[\text{CO}_2]$ had a smaller effect on g_s of C_3 plants under soil water deficit than under well-watered conditions (Gunderson et al., 2002). In good agreement with this, here the $e[\text{CO}_2]$

Fig. 5. Relationship between WUE_{int} , WUE_{ins} and WUE_b of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34; Az34 was expressed as “A” in the present figure) under three N-fertilization regimes (N-fertilization at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ (400 ppm, expressed as “a” in the present figure) and $e[\text{CO}_2]$ (800 ppm, expressed as “e” in the present figure). ** denotes significance of the regression line at $p < 0.01$.

Table 3

Hundred-grain weight, grain yield, harvest index (HI) and WUE_g of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertigation regimes (N-fertigation at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm). Significant probabilities for variables and the interaction of factors were analyzed according to three-way ANOVA by Duncan's test. *, **, *** and ns denote significances at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$ and no significance, respectively.

Genotype	[CO ₂]	N-fertigation	Hundred-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g)	HI	WUE _g (g L ⁻¹)
WT	400	FIN	5.62 ± 0.07	16.49 ± 1.03	0.37 ± 0.02	1.48 ± 0.08
		DIN	5.73 ± 0.23	14.46 ± 0.76	0.42 ± 0.02	1.67 ± 0.09
		PRDN	6.04 ± 0.17	17.98 ± 0.74	0.44 ± 0.01	1.99 ± 0.11
	800	FIN	6.39 ± 0.13	14.91 ± 1.48	0.29 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.08
		DIN	6.50 ± 0.16	16.46 ± 1.56	0.34 ± 0.04	1.83 ± 0.18
		PRDN	6.20 ± 0.06	17.05 ± 2.27	0.33 ± 0.04	1.89 ± 0.22
Az34	400	FIN	5.86 ± 0.23	12.88 ± 2.91	0.27 ± 0.06	0.95 ± 0.23
		DIN	5.73 ± 0.34	16.80 ± 2.84	0.37 ± 0.04	1.55 ± 0.23
		PRDN	5.94 ± 0.20	20.71 ± 0.38	0.46 ± 0.02	1.93 ± 0.07
	800	FIN	5.97 ± 0.24	10.39 ± 1.20	0.18 ± 0.01	0.83 ± 0.09
		DIN	6.50 ± 0.24	18.04 ± 3.30	0.34 ± 0.04	1.84 ± 0.31
		PRDN	6.15 ± 0.14	16.19 ± 2.74	0.33 ± 0.05	1.66 ± 0.28
ANOVA analysis						
Genotype			ns	ns	*	*
[CO ₂]			**	ns	***	ns
N-fertigation			ns	*	***	***
Genotype × [CO ₂]			ns	ns	ns	ns
Genotype × N-fertigation			ns	ns	ns	ns
[CO ₂] × N-fertigation			ns	ns	ns	ns
Genotype × [CO ₂] × N-fertigation			ns	ns	ns	ns

Fig. 6. N uptake and ¹⁵N uptake of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertigation regimes (N-fertigation at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm). Different letters on the columns indicate statistically significant differences among the treatments by Duncan's test at $p < 0.05$.

had little effect on g_s of WT, especially under DIN and PRDN, compared to a[CO₂] (Fig. 3b). It is widely accepted that plants grown at e[CO₂] had a higher A_n compared with that at a[CO₂] (Ainsworth and Rogers, 2007; Leakey et al., 2009; Mamatha et al., 2014). Consistent with this, the results from the present study showed that e[CO₂] significantly increased A_n compared with a[CO₂] regardless of genotypes and N-fertigation regimes (Fig. 3a). The e[CO₂] can stimulate carboxylation reaction and inhibit oxygenation reaction of Rubisco, hereby enhancing A_n of C₃ plants (Long et al., 2004; Ainsworth and Rogers, 2007). Consequently, the e[CO₂] increased WUE of both genotypes at stomatal level as well as at leaf level, compared with a[CO₂], in line with the finding of earlier studies (Pazzagli et al., 2016). At e[CO₂], the increased WUE of WT at stomatal level and leaf level was attributed to enhanced A_n . For Az34, the positive effect of e[CO₂] on WUE was attributed to both significantly enhanced A_n and lowered g_s and T_r (Fig. 3). Briefly, the reduced irrigation regimes combined with e[CO₂] further enhanced WUE of both genotypes at stomatal level at e[CO₂] as a result of the increase in A_n and the decrease in g_s (Fig. 3), in line with the results of earlier studies on spring wheat and cotton (Kang et al., 2002).

Webb and Hetherington (1997) found that the stomatal closure induced by e[CO₂] of *Arabidopsis thaliana* ABA-deficient mutant aba1

was similar to wild type plants. Merilo et al. (2013) observed that *Arabidopsis thaliana* aba1 and aba3 mutants kept the stomatal closure in response to e[CO₂]. However, the [ABA]_{leaf} of *Arabidopsis thaliana* aba1 and aba3 are ca. 17% and 33% of [ABA]_{leaf} of the corresponding wild type (Koornneef and Jorna, 1982), and the small amount of ABA in these mutants may be enough to mediate the e[CO₂]-induced stomatal closure. Similarly, Chater et al. (2015) reported that *nced3* and *nced5* ABA-deficient plants of *Arabidopsis thaliana* with extremely low [ABA]_{leaf} (ca. 1.5% of its corresponding wild type) could not close stomata in response to e[CO₂] while the stomatal apertures of its corresponding wild type was decreased by 27% under e[CO₂]. Thus, ABA is involved in the process of CO₂-induced stomatal closure and the sensitivity of stomatal closure to e[CO₂] decreases in the case of reduced ABA (Chater et al., 2015). Similarly, our recent studies have revealed that the endogenous ABA level of tomato and barley played an essential role in modulating the response of g_s to soil water deficits under e[CO₂] (Fang et al., 2019; Wei et al., 2020). In the present study, the endogenous ABA levels of both genotypes were not affected by e[CO₂], and the e[CO₂]-induced reduction of g_s in Az34 possibly indicated that the ABA level in Az34 was sufficient to mediate the e[CO₂]-induced stomatal closure (Figs. 3b, 4b). Also, the decreased g_s of Az34 at e[CO₂] was

Fig. 7. ¹⁵N partitioning to grains, stems and leaves of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertilization regimes (N-fertilization at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm). Different letters on the columns indicate statistically significant differences among the treatments by Duncan's test at $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 8. ¹⁵N recovery rate of two barley genotypes (WT and Az34) under three N-fertilization regimes (N-fertilization at full irrigation volume, FIN; N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, DIN; alternate N-fertilization at reduced irrigation volume, PRDN) at a[CO₂] (400 ppm) and e[CO₂] (800 ppm).

possibly related to an ABA-independent pathway (Hsu et al., 2018) or to the increase in xylem sap pH, which can intensify the root-to-shoot ABA signaling (Fang et al., 2019).

The e[CO₂], acted as “C fertilizer”, can significantly improve shoot biomass of C₃ plants (Wu et al., 2004; Ziska et al., 2004; Mamatha et al., 2014; Pazzagli et al., 2016). Consistent with this, the results from the present study showed that the e[CO₂] significantly enhanced shoot dry biomass of both genotypes compared to a[CO₂], which was mainly attributed to the enhanced A_n, increased net assimilation rate or improved relative growth rate under e[CO₂] (Chowdhury et al., 2005; Yelle et al., 1990). Earlier studies have shown that the e[CO₂] can improve plant water status by alleviating the negative effects of drought, leading to an increase in carbon gain (Wall et al., 2001). Likewise, the results from the present study showed a less reduction in shoot dry biomass due to reduced irrigation of WT at e[CO₂] (6% in DIN and 2% in PRDN) compared to that at a[CO₂] (23% in DIN and 8% in PRDN) (Table 2). At a[CO₂], Az34 had higher plant water use than WT as a

result of larger g_s and T_r (Fig. 3b, c; Table 2). However, the plant water use of Az34 was reduced significantly under e[CO₂] as a result of a decrease in g_s and T_r regulated by e[CO₂] (Fig. 3b, c; Table 2). Accumulated evidence has revealed that reduced irrigation can reduce plant water use compared to full irrigation by decreasing g_s as well as T_r of plants (Pazzagli et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020), consistent with the results from the present study. The increase of WUE_b of WT at e[CO₂] was mainly due to the increased shoot dry biomass but not to the decreased plant water use (Table 2). For Az34, increased WUE_b at e[CO₂] was mainly attributed to enhanced shoot dry biomass as well as decreased plant water use (Table 2). Previous studies have shown that plants grown under moderate drought stress had higher WUE_b than that under well-watered conditions (Li et al., 2020), owing to a less reduction in shoot dry biomass (11.9% in DIN and 6.9% in PRDN) than in plant water use (24.1% in DIN and 22.2% in PRDN), in line with the findings in the present study. Across the genotypes and [CO₂] treatments, WUE_b of plants grown under DIN and PRDN treatments was 13.8% and 17.9% higher than that of FIN treatment, respectively. Obviously, plants grown under PRDN showed a slight enhancement of WUE_b compared to that under DIN, and which was mainly due to the fact that the shoot dry biomass of PRDN treatment was higher than that of DIN treatment under the similar amount of water consumption (Table 2). The improved shoot biomass of PRDN plants could be related to the enhanced A_n by improving plant N status (Wang et al., 2010; Fig. 3a). In addition, the significantly positive relationship between WUE_{int} and WUE_b, or between WUE_{ins} and WUE_b, indicates that the changes of WUE at whole plant level were closely related to stomatal control over gas exchange rates, consistent with the findings reported in winter wheat (Wang et al., 2013b).

The e[CO₂] enhanced hundred-grain weight of both genotypes in the present study, which was similar to that reported in rice (Madan et al., 2012) and wheat (Högy et al., 2013), and such effect could be attributed to a faster grain-filling rate (Li et al., 2000). Although the e[CO₂] increased A_n as well as shoot dry biomass, the grain yield was not affected by e[CO₂], consequently, the plants grown at e[CO₂] possessed a lower HI than that at a[CO₂] (Fig. 3a; Tables 2, 3). Although excessive soil moisture (2400 m³ ha⁻¹) could reduce wheat yield (Guo et al., 2019), a moderate soil water deficit may promote the remobilization of carbon from vegetative tissues to grains hereby accelerating the grain-filling rate of rice and wheat during the later grain-filling period (Yang et al., 2006). Specifically, the elevated ABA levels of crops under drought stress could stimulate the activity of key enzymes involved in the sucrose-to-starch metabolic pathway in the grains, promoting grain filling and partitioning of carbon into grains, though a high concentration of ABA caused by severe drought stress could be harmful to grain filling (Yang et al., 2001, 2002, 2004; Yang and Zhang, 2006). Guo et al. (2019) reported that reduced irrigation (irrigated with 80% of the water consumed in the local conventional irrigation) increased grain yield and HI by 4.3% and 8.9%, respectively. In accordance with this, the results from the present study showed that DIN and PRDN significantly enhanced grain yield as well as HI compared with FIN (Table 3). Such effect was most probably due to the acceleration of the grain-filling rate and the enhanced remobilization of carbon from vegetative tissues to grains mediated by high ABA level in the plants (Yang et al., 2001, 2002, 2004; Yang and Zhang, 2006). Consequently, plants grown under DIN and PRDN had higher WUE_g than that under FIN as a result of the improved grain yield and the reduced plant water use (Tables 2, 3), consistent with the findings of earlier study (Wang et al., 2013b). Across the genotype and [CO₂] treatments, WUE_g of plants grown under DIN and PRDN treatments was 50.1% and 62.7% higher than that of FIN treatment, respectively. Compared to DIN plants, the higher WUE_g of PRDN plants was mainly attributed to the enhanced grain yield under PRDN caused by the improved A_n (Fig. 3a, Table 3).

Earlier studies have shown that the plant N concentration can be reduced by e[CO₂], due to the dilution of tissue N by increased photosynthetic carbon assimilation or the decrease in N uptake by decreased

transpiration (Taub et al., 2008). Also, the decrease in plant N demand at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ has been reported by Stitt and Krapp (1999). In the present study, N uptake of WT was decreased by DIN and PRDN at $a[\text{CO}_2]$ while a slight increase in that was found at $e[\text{CO}_2]$, which could be attributed mainly to a higher N demand caused by the increase in plant biomass accumulation under $e[\text{CO}_2]$ (Table 2). This indicated that reduced irrigation regimes, especially PRDN, had positively affected N uptake under $e[\text{CO}_2]$ and alleviated the negative effect of $e[\text{CO}_2]$ on plant N nutrition. In addition, partitioning of N between grain and straw is important in crops, which mainly depends on the partitioning of dry matter between the vegetative and reproductive organs (Desai and Bhatia, 1978). In the present study, plants of both genotypes grown under DIN and PRDN allocated more N into the grain mainly due to high HI compared to the FIN plants (Fig. 7). ^{15}N recovery rate has been used to reflect plant ability to acquire applied N fertilizer from soil (Baligar et al., 2001). Here, at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ plants of both genotypes had a slight greater ^{15}N recovery rate under reduced irrigation regimes compared to FIN, which was attributed mainly to the increased N uptake under reduced irrigation regimes (Figs. 6, 8).

5. Conclusions

The two genotypes showed different responses to reduced fertigation regimes, especially at $e[\text{CO}_2]$. Although $e[\text{CO}_2]$ had little effect on g_s , T_r as well as plant water use of WT, especially under DIN and PRDN, it increased A_n , resulting in an increased WUE at stomatal, leaf and whole plant levels. For Az34, the positive effect of $e[\text{CO}_2]$ on WUE was attributed to both significantly enhanced A_n and lowered g_s and T_r . For both genotypes, $e[\text{CO}_2]$ increased 100-grain weight and shoot dry biomass but didn't affect grain yield and WUE for grain production. PRDN increased grain yield, HI and WUE_g of both genotypes regardless of $[\text{CO}_2]$, compared to FIN. DIN and PRDN increased N uptake of both genotypes at $e[\text{CO}_2]$ compared to FIN. Likewise, compared to $a[\text{CO}_2]$, $e[\text{CO}_2]$ increased ^{15}N uptake and ^{15}N recovery rate of both genotypes by enhancing biomass accumulation. In addition, both genotypes grown under DIN and PRDN allocated more N to the grain compared to the FIN plants. Collectively, N-fertigation at reduced irrigation volume promoted N allocation to the grain and increased WUE, particularly under $e[\text{CO}_2]$. Reduced irrigation regimes, especially PRDN, are recommended for optimizing WUE and N nutrition of crops in a future water-limited and CO_2 -enriched environment.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The research was partially funded by National Key Research and Development Program of China (grant no. 2018YFE0107000), China Scholarship Council (201903250088) and the Sino-Danish Center for Education and Research (SDC). We thank Lene Korsholm Jørgensen for technical assistance.

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